

RISK ANALYSIS AND DECISION MAKING PROCESS IN AGRICULTURAL ENTERPRISE OF THE REPUBLIC OF SERBIA

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SUMMARY: Profit is the most important aim of the agricultural enterprise. It is in connection with creation of the Value on the market and with the process of its confirming on the financial market. So in the paper is discussing the logic of financing the agricultural enterprises growth in the transition country and making the comparisons with the level of risk acceptable, nature of the offered financing and the decision making process. Such analysis is representing additional guidance to the managers and its investment decisions under the conditions of extreme instability and risk.

Key words: Agriculture, Enterprises, Risk analysis, Decision Making.

INTRODUCTION

The essence of the corporate philosophy is based on treating the enterprise as a widely opened system (Djuričin, 4). It presumes creation of the mechanism and providing conditions for the functioning of the simulative macroeconomic and market oriented system created by the government, on one side, and on the other side, declaration of business risk and all the relevant consequences to the enterprise or to its owners. Understanding of those preposition is one of the main issues for the agricultural enterprises in the countries under transition.

Privatization of the state owned an so called social owned agricultural enterprises is one of the basic goals in the process of creating the corporative structure of the enterprises and in orientation toward market economy. Non defined ownership is one of the main sources of the business risk in the enterprises and limitation for the defining the financial requirements and creating the profit. It is the source for the instability of the enterprise, its inefficiency and low competitiveness. On the other side, in such condi-

Original scientific paper / *Originalni naučni rad*

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tions, raises the number of sponsors of the enterprise who are bearing the consequences of the inefficient business orientation.

As it is stated, uncertainty and the sources of uncertainty in the agricultural enterprises could be expressed through description of phenomenon, but the quantitative data very often are insufficient to be incorporated into the analysis and to help the management to govern an agricultural enterprise in a profit manner. The result of this statement is that risk analysis must provide to the owners of the enterprise quantitative elements to judge the risk of any business decision or project implementation. So we can define the risk of the project as the probable variability of its future returns. For the variable such as sales from which future returns are derived, sales risk can be defined as the variability of expected sales. In practice, during project analysis, there are usually several variables for which doubts exist as to their best estimates. The purpose of risk analysis is to help management to isolate the risks and provide a means by which the various project outcomes can be reduced to a format from which a decision can be made. So, the final consequence of risk analysis is opinion or judgments regarding the possible range of future returns on investments in agricultural enterprises, as well as the possibility of each value to be created within this range.

But besides the possibility of evaluation the business risk of one project, often there is a need for judgment of all expected risks in the agricultural enterprise, portfolio risk. The agricultural enterprises portfolio risk can be analyzed also by considering the relationship between the proposed project and the existing investments and operations of the company. It must be stressed that in spite of judging the project as a risk one, it could be accepted for implementation on the basis of portfolio risk analysis. But this type of analysis is out of our interest in this paper.

METHODS FOR QUANTIFYING RISK

In the particular project or in the companies portfolio risk could be usually analyzed by running the three common methods of risk analysis: method of probability distribution; method of simulation; and method of sensitivity analysis (Krasulja, 6).

Method of probability distribution: Risk is associated with variability of returns expected. So, the more variable are the expected future returns, the riskier is the investment or project, an vice versa. However, it is useful to define risk more precisely. In the case of any investment decision or any kind of business decision, it has to be done forecast of future events. Probability expectation could be defined or measured from the point of view of a project analyst, or as an expectation of each possibly outcome. In its simplest form, a probability distribution could consists of an optimistic, pessimistic and most likely estimate or alternatively, high (boom), low (recession) and a “best guess” (normal market conditions) estimates.

Method of Simulation: When cash flows are correlated over time, the calculation of standard deviation will not give a correct result of the Net Present Value (NPV) variation of projects or / and Internal rate of return (IRR). The mathematic explication of NPV and equation for calculating the IRR is:

$$NPV = \sum_{n=1}^n C F_n (1 + r)^{-n} - C_0$$

$$C_0 = CF_1 / (1 + r)^1 + CF_2 / (1 + r)^2 + \dots + CF_n / (1 + r)^n \text{ where:}$$

CF_n – cash flow in any period n (year 1,2,3, ...),

r - rate of return or interest rate:

C – value of the project;

C_0 – investments

Also, in practice, it may be necessary to produce separate probabilities for alternative sales revenue, different items of costs, and different possible life spans. These problems can be solved by using Monte Carlo simulation analysis, by the computer, which allows the consideration of many variables and their probability distributions as a result taking in account in the risk analysis as a part of the process of decision making in the agricultural enterprises.

Method of Sensitivity Analysis: The purpose of sensitivity analysis is to define the variables to which the NPV of the project in agricultural enterprise is most sensitive, and it is normally used to measure the extent to which these variables can change before the investment results in a negative NPV. Sensitivity analysis is useful for determining consequences of specified changes in variables such as product price, sales volume, input costs and investment life span. However, only risk analysis can provide any indication of the likelihood that such events will actually occur. Also, break-even analysis can be viewed as a form of sensitivity analysis. It enables the analyst to determine the impact of changes in cost, production volume and price on profits of the agricultural enterprise. The standard mathematical expression of the method is:

$P - S(p - mc - vc) - Fc$, where:

P = profit;

mc = material costs;

S = Sales

vc = variable costs,

p = selling price;

Fc = fixed costs

Sensitivity analysis is carried out by replacing the input variables that determine profitability with their expected values given in feasibility studies in order to determine profitability in quantitative terms.

RESULTS

As a graphical method of risk analysis the *Method of probability distribution* is showing the connection between actual investments in agricultural project and returns expected.

Such relation is shown in the next examples illustrated as it is shown below:

Example 1. Pay-off matrix for Project X and Project Y

State of the Market	Annual cash flow	
	Projekat X	Projekat Y
	RSD – Currency (dinars)	
Boom (high)	1.200	2.000
Normal (most likely)	1.000	1.000
Recession (low)	800	0

Source: Authors

The probability expectation in the example is: in case of boom is 0.2, in normal conditions is 0.6, and probability of recession is 0.2. Given the annual cash flows under the three possible states of the future market and their probability of occurring, weighted average projected cash flows can be calculated by multiplying each cash flow by its probability of occurrence (see below).

Example 2. Calculation of expected values

Appraisal	Cash flow	Probability	Weighted average or Expected Value
Project X			
<i>Boom</i>	1.200	0.2	240
<i>Normal</i>	1.000	0.6	600
<i>Recession</i>	800	0.2	160
Project Y			
<i>Boom</i>	2.000	0.2	400
<i>Normal</i>	1.000	0.6	600
<i>Recession</i>	0	0.2	0

Source: Authors

Calculated average value is defined as expected value of cash flow in particular investment or any business operation of the agricultural enterprise. Also, it could be stated as a basic result in comparison with the values created through alternative business decisions.

Business risk always exists due to the particular investment and could be presented in graphical form to obtain a clear picture of variability of actual outcomes (Graph 1).

Assume two mutually exclusive projects P_x and P_y which are with the same net cash flows of USD 4.000. In the same time, it could be two following cases: investment project P_x has probability of cash inflows in the range of USD 3.000 - USD 9.000 while investment project P_y has probability in the range of USD 0 - USD 12.000. Looking at the net cash flow (which is equal in both cases), one is tempted to rank both investments equally. But a look at the graph above shows that the variability of cash flows for project P_y is greater than of project P_x and therefore the project P_y is riskier project.

Source: Authors

Graph 1. Probability of Cash Flow

The variability of distribution is normally measured by standard deviation. The earlier example is used to calculate the standard deviation as presented below (example 3).

Example 3. Calculation of Standard Deviation

Probability	Calculation of Standard Deviation		RSD		
	Net Cash Flow	Expected value (1 x 2)	Deviation	Standard deviation	Variance (1 x 5)
<i>1</i>	<i>2</i>	<i>3</i>	<i>4</i>	<i>5</i>	<i>6</i>
Project X					
0.2	1,200	240	200	40,000	8,000
0.6	1,000	600	0	0	0
0.2	800	160	(200)	40,000	8,000
expected value	1.000			variance	16.000
Standard deviation					126.49
Project Y					
0.2	2,000	400	1,000	1,000,000	200,000
0.6	1,000	600	0	0	0
0.2	0	0	(1,000)	1,000,000	200,000
expected value	1.000			variance	400.000
standard deviation					632.45

Source: Authors

Columns 1, 2 and 3 are taken directly from previous example. In column 4, the expected value from each possible outcome is subtracted to derive the deviations about the expected value. In column 5, deviations are squared. In column 6, squared deviation is multiplied by associated probability and the products are summed to obtain the variance of the probability distribution.

The calculation provide outcomes for $P_x = \text{USD } 126.49$ and $P_y = 632.45$. So, it could be stated that the project P_y is bringing a higher risk than project P_x .

Method of Sensitivity Analysis: In the implementation of this method management of the agricultural enterprise should pay special attention and control those variables to which NPV is particularly sensitive. In our example, it can be used the simplest type of sensitivity analysis with variables that are influencing profitability as follows:

Example 4. Sensitivity analysis

Variable	Best estimate	Increasing variable by 10%	Resulting profit RSD	Change in profit %	Rank order of variables
Sales (unit)	10,000	11,000	120,000	20	2
Price (USD/unit)	50	55	150,000	50	1
Variable Costs (USD/unit)					
– raw material	10	11	90,000	(10)	3
– other variable costs	20	22	80,000	(20)	2
Fixed costs (USD)	100,000	110,000	90,000	(10)	3
Pofit (USD)	100,000				

Source: Authors

The profit is calculated on the basis of 10% increase in variables, taking each variable at a time.

The sensitivity analysis based on a discounted cash flow model is presented in the next example:

Example 5. Implementation of the method of Sensitivity analysis based on DNT

Cash flow	Year 0	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3
	RSD	RSD	RSD	RSD
Cost of equipment	(100,000)	0	0	0
50.000 kom USD 2/ kom	0	100,000	100,000	100,000
Variable costs	0	50,000	50,000	50,000
Net cash flow	(100,000)	50,000	50,000	50,000
The cost of capital is 12% and the NPV is RSD 20.095				

Source: Authors

The calculated variables are:

- 1) *Sales volume.* The net cash flow will have to fall to RSD 41.634 (RSD 100.000/2.4019 discount factor) for the NPV to be zero, because it will be zero when the present value of the future cash flow is RSD 100.000. The discount factors for 12% and Years 1,2 and 3 are 0.8929; 0.7972; and 0.7118 respectively. As the likely net cash flow is + RSD 50.000, the net cash flow may decline by about RSD 8.366 each year before NPV becomes zero. Total sales revenue may therefore drop by RSD 16.732 (net cash flow = 50% of sales). At selling price of RSD 2 per product, this represents 8.366 units. Alternatively, the sales volume may decline by 16.7% before the NPV becomes negative.
- 2) *Product price.* When the sales volume is RSD 50.000 products yearly, total sales revenue can drop to RSD 91.634 (100.000 - 8.366) before the NPV becomes negative. This represents a selling price of RSD 1.83 or a reduction of approximately RSD 0.17 per product which represents about 8.4% reduction in selling price.
- 3) *Variable costs.* The total variable costs can increase by RSD 8.366 or RSD 0.17 per product. This represent increase of 17%.
- 4) *Initial outlay.* The total outlay can increase by the NPV before the investment breaks even. The initial outlay may therefore increase by RSD 20.095 or 20%.
- 5) *Cost of capital.* IRR for the project is nearly 30%. Consequently, the cost of capital can increase by 250% before the NPV becomes zero.

The above analysis can be summarized as follows:

Variable	Switching value (%)	Variable	Switching value (%)
Sales Volume	16.7	Initial outlay	20.0
Selling price	8.4	Cost of capital	200.0
Variable costs	17.0		

Source: Authors

The element to which the NPV appears to be most sensitive is the price followed by sales volume and variable cost.

DISCUSSION

The implementation of the *Method of probability distribution* could erase certain problems in the use of standard deviation as a measure of risk. Taking in account an example which shows the probability distributions for investments P_{x1} and P_{y1} . Assume that P_{x1} has an expected return of RSD 2.000 and standard deviation of RSD 600, and investment P_{y1} also with the same standard deviation of RSD 600 has higher expected return of RSD 8.000. Investment P_{y1} has more risk per RSD of the return than P_{x1} . On this basis, it is reasonable to assign a higher degree of risk to investment P_{y1} than to investment P_{x1} , event though both have identical standard deviations. So, it must be derived the standard deviation by the expected value of net cash flows to obtain the coefficient of variation, to handle this problem. For investment P_{y1} , RSD 600 is divided by RSD 2.000 (expected value), obtaining 0.30 as the coefficient of variation and 0.075 for project P_{x1} which is much lower coefficient of variation. So the later project has been less risky than previous.

In the implementation of the *Method of Simulation* the scope of simulation analysis is connected with providing the probability distribution for Cash Flows (CF), internal rate of return (IRR) and net present value (NPV). This method is using often and the interpretation is so common that we decided not to present this method particular.

Method of Sensitivity Analysis: In the case of the sensitivity calculation which is based on the increase in variables of 10% and parallel taking of each variable at a time, it could be pointed out that if the change of variables is equal by percentage, profit is most sensitive to changes in price. It is followed by sales volumes and other variable costs with similar changes, and at last with the same level of changes in case of raw material and fixed costs ranking. Although this simple analysis has pointed the most sensitive variables, no insight is provided into the probability of these changes taking place. For example, the average of 10% increase in row material cost may be very high while the probability of a 10% increase in product price may be low. In the case of sensitivity analysis based on a discounted cash flow model, it could be shown that it is important for the project sponsor to pay particular attention to the items like sales volume, selling price and variable costs so that can be fully monitored. Sensitivity analysis has a number of shortages. In particular, the method requires that changes in each key variable are isolated, but the management is also interested in the combined effect of changes of two or more variables. In addition, the method is giving no indication to the likely probability of changes in key variables or of a combination of variables occurring.

CONCLUSION

The transition process involves new relations in running the agricultural enterprises. Privatization and clear ownership are forcing the owners of the firm and managers to restructure the enterprise and make it more efficient. But, in the process of judging the business possibilities, they are faced with the higher risk than earlier. Business risk is caused by the internal and external variables and with its occurring. So, besides running the profit of the firm, owners and the managers are faced with certainty of its making.

When we talk about possible methods discussed it could be concluded that in connection between actual investments in agricultural project and returns expected the

method of probability distribution could efficiently help in determination of probability distributions for investments (P_{x1} and P_{y1}). Parallel, for the probability distribution for Cash Flows (CF), internal rate of return (IRR) and net present value (NPV) the best solution could be using the method of simulation. From the calculation, certain conclusions can be derived such as: “the likelihood is 80% that IRR will equal 12% “or” there is a 10% chance that the project will result in loss of RSD 35.000”, etc. Finally, in the case of sensitivity analysis method implementation it is possible to take care of particular items like sales volume, selling price and variable costs and on that basis monitor the possible risks in spite of a number of possible shortages.

Implementation of those methods for quantifying the risk could bring more stable conditions for agribusiness enterprises that are operating even at higher risk than other enterprises. This is an important and relevant aspect of the problem of creating the profit and enabling the agricultural enterprise growth. Such methods are providing necessary tools for the managers and owners of the firms for its better management and better decision making. In that process, one can identify the level of risk but also the certainty and possibility of creating the cash flow in the agricultural enterprise.

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ANALIZA RIZIKA I PROCES DONOŠENJA ODLUKA U POLJOPRIVREDNOM PREDUZEĆU U REPUBLICI SRBIJI

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Izvod

Profit je najznačajniji cilj poljoprivrednog preduzeća. On je povezan sa stvaranjem vrednosti i njenog potvrđivanja na tržištu. Stoga se u radu diskutuje logika finansiranja rasta poljoprivrednog preduzeća u zemlji koja se nalazi u tranziciji i pravi komparacija sa nivoom prihvatljivog rizika, prirodnom finansiranja i procesom donošenja odluka. Ovakva analiza predstavlja dodatni vodič za menadžere i njihove investicione odluke u uslovima ekstremne nestabilnosti i rizika.

Ključne reči: poljoprivreda, preduzeća, analiza rizika, donošenje odluka.

Received / *Primljen*: 19.01.2011.

Accepted / *Prihvaćen*: 16.02.2011.